

MINDSET, ANXIETY, AND PSYCHOLOGICAL WELL-BEING OF SAINT MARY'S UNIVERSITY SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Mindset, Anxiety, and Psychological Well-Being of Saint Mary's University Senior High School Students

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Abstract

Mental health has become a controversial topic worldwide. The social media, pandemic, and societal trends are found to have strong link to the rise of mental health conditions. Mental health shows a paramount importance to the overall well-being of an individual and significantly affected by the mindset, anxiety, and psychological well-being. This study aims to determine the relationship among mindset, anxiety, and psychological well-being of senior high school students at Saint Mary's University. The descriptive, comparative, and correlational research designs and thematic analysis were utilized in analyzing the quantitative and qualitative data gathered from the 508 senior high school students. Findings reveal that students predominantly have growth mindset with some fixed ideas and experienced moderate levels of anxiety but they have high psychological well-being. Moreover, it is found that there is a significant difference in the type of mindset based on academic standing ($p=.005$), the level of anxiety based on sex ($p=.001$) and strands ($p=.007$), and the level of psychological well-being based on socioeconomic status ($p=.026$). Furthermore, results shows that there is a significant relationship between mindset and psychological well-being ($r=.366$, $p=.000$). However, it is found that there is no significant relationship between mindset and anxiety and anxiety and psychological well-being. Further research is needed to understand the complex relationship between mindset, anxiety, and psychological well-being, as well as to develop effective interventions to support students' mental health.

Keywords: *mindset, anxiety, psychological well-being*

Introduction

Mental health has become a controversial topic throughout the whole world. There has been a rise in mental health conditions due to social media, the coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) pandemic, and societal trends. Despite the positive aspects of social media, several studies have found a strong link between heavy social media and an increased risk for depression, anxiety, loneliness, self-harm, and even suicidal thoughts. A 2019 study in the United States of America found that those who spent more than three hours a day using social media might be at heightened risk for mental health problems (Riehm et al., 2022). Moreover, during the COVID-19 pandemic, many people have experienced insomnia, anxiety, and depression. The implementation of lockdown has been associated with stressors such as financial problems, loneliness, fear, helplessness, and frustration leading to a spike in the number of individuals having mental health problems. Furthermore, societal trends also link to the rise in mental disorders as people want to feel a sense of belonging. Individuals tend to follow the standards set by society even if it causes serious harm to them.

The World Health Organization (WHO, 2022) defined mental health as a state of mental well-being that enables people to cope with the stresses of life, realize their abilities, learn well and work well, and contribute to their community. It is an integral part of an individual that helps them to have a healthful living and attain personal development. Mental health is crucial for people to make healthy choices, accomplish tasks effectively, and socialize with other people, which helps in reaching their full potential. It is also associated with the absence of mental health illness which significantly contributes to positive well-being and to creating a balanced life.

According to WHO (n.d), exposure to unfavorable social, economic, geopolitical, and environmental circumstances – including poverty, violence, inequality, and environmental deprivation – increases people's risk of experiencing mental health conditions. Moreover, in the World Mental Health Report published by WHO (2021), about one in eight people in the world live with a mental disorder. Mental health disorders became rampant in adolescents over the span of time mainly due to social media use. In fact, it is estimated that one in seven (14%) 10–19-year-olds experience mental health conditions, yet these remain largely unrecognized and untreated (WHO, 2022). Most people do not have access to effective care due to a lack of financial capacity. Also, treatment is often poor in quality which inadequately addresses the needs of people with mental health disorders.

Mental health illness may result in social exclusion, discrimination, stigma, risk-taking behaviors, educational difficulties, and others (WHO, 2021). It may cause disturbance to one's life, resulting in an inability to perform well. The National Statistics Office (NSO) identifies mental health illnesses as the third most common form of morbidity among Filipinos (Lally et al., 2021). The COVID-19 outbreak was associated with a high prevalence of anxiety and depression symptoms. Around 3.6 million Filipinos are suffering from mental disorders amid the coronavirus pandemic, according to initial results of the survey by the Department of Health (DOH, 2020). This was mainly due to the isolation felt and lack of social involvement as restrictions were implemented to minimize the spreading of the deadly disease.

Moreover, a survey conducted with 1879 respondents from the Philippines resulted in 16.3% of the respondents rating the psychological impact of the pandemic as moderate-to-severe, 16.9% reported depression symptoms as moderate-to-severe, 28.8% reported anxiety

levels as moderate-to-severe, and lastly, 13.4% reported moderate-to-severe stress levels wherein students where one of the factors in the survey conducted (Sison et al., 2022).

Furthermore, according to the study of Alibudbud (2021), Filipino college students are at risk for depressive and anxiety disorders were 35% and 47.2%, respectively. Experiencing difficulties coping with studies was associated with significant depressive symptoms and anxiety problems with an index of determination of 8.5% to 18.6%.

Mental health plays an important role in student success. It was found that lower depression and higher psychological well-being were consistently associated with better academic performance and education behaviors (Duncan et al., 2021). This shows the paramount importance of mental health in the overall well-being and functioning of a person. Mental health is important at every stage of life, from childhood and adolescence through adulthood (Mental Health CDC, 2023). Moreover, mindset, anxiety, and psychological well-being are believed to have significance in understanding the mental health of an individual.

Mindset

Mindset is a concept that affects a person's mental health. In Merriam- Webster's Dictionary (n.d.), mindset is defined as a mental attitude or inclination of a person. It also refers to the state of mind that influences how people think about and then enact their goal-directed activities in ways that may systematically promote or interfere with optimal functioning (APA Dictionary of Psychology, n.d.). Additionally, mindset is a set of assumptions that aid in the distillation of complicated worldviews into digestible knowledge, as well as a set of expectations.

Moreover, mindsets can aid with information distillation and expectation management. They can also be maladaptive, resulting in interpersonal issues and emotions of guilt, inadequacy, sadness, and anxiety. According to Towery (2021), mindsets are incredibly malleable, and if they are willing to learn the technique of altering their mentality and conquering their misguided thoughts, they can dramatically increase their happiness.

Furthermore, mindset refers to a person's established attitudes, beliefs, and perspectives that shape their thoughts, behaviors, and overall approach to life. Moreover, it encompasses the way an individual perceives and interprets the world around them, as well as their responses to various situations, challenges, and opportunities. One influential framework for understanding mindsets was developed by psychologist Carol S. Dweck (2006), who identified two primary types: fixed and growth mindsets. In a fixed mindset, individuals believe that their abilities, intelligence, and talents are fixed traits that cannot be significantly changed or developed. They tend to avoid challenges, fear failure, and view setbacks as indications of personal limitations. This mindset can lead to a desire to prove oneself, a tendency to avoid effortful tasks, and a resistance to feedback or criticism. On the other hand, in a growth mindset, individuals believe that their abilities and intelligence can be cultivated and improved through dedication, effort, and learning. They embrace challenges, view failures as opportunities for growth, and seek out new experiences to expand their skills. This mindset fosters resilience, motivation, and a willingness to learn from mistakes.

Nowadays, mindset directly or indirectly comes from our upbringing, past experiences, learning environment, beliefs, social norms, and culture (Partners, 2018). Mindsets depict significant relationships with factors including gender, family relationships, socioeconomic status, birth order, and academic standing. Moreover, the pandemic and social media also affect the students' mindset.

Recently, the COVID-19 pandemic affected the mindset of all individuals. During the height of the pandemic, schools were closed resulting in the change of learning modality around the world. Students' growth mindset is tied to the help they receive from the individuals they deal with regularly, and this may thus be regarded as a contextual element for growing their intellect or ability. Amidst the present COVID-19 pandemic, teacher assistance creates a secure learning environment for students, even if this does not occur through face-to-face interaction (Jiang et al., 2023).

Additionally, in today's communication environment, social media has become a crucial component of people's lives, especially students. Its usage is increasing more than ever before, particularly in the post-pandemic era, which is distinguished by a huge upheaval in educational institutions. According to recent social media research, roughly three (3) billion people worldwide are currently conversing via social media (Iwamoto & Chun, 2020). Though social media has provided wonderful opportunities for sharing ideas and feelings, the type of social support may fall short of meeting students' emotional requirements, or the stated good benefits may be transient (Chen & Xiao, 2022). According to Iwamoto and Chun (2020), when students are affected by social media posts, especially given the increasing reliance on social media in everyday life, they may be encouraged to begin comparing themselves to others or develop unrealistic expectations of themselves or others, which can have a variety of affective consequences. Learners' mental repertoires can be formed and expanded by how they feel. As a result, their cognitive repertoire and mental ability may become limited, and they may lose attention while learning (Chen & Xiao, 2022).

Lastly, it is important to note that mindset is not solely limited to intelligence or abilities; it also encompasses beliefs about personal qualities, relationships, success, and other areas of life. Mindsets can have a significant impact on how individuals approach their goals, handle obstacles, and ultimately achieve success or fulfillment. Developing a growth mindset can lead to increased motivation, resilience, and a willingness to take on challenges, as individuals believe in their capacity to learn and grow. Mindset is not a fixed attribute but can be influenced and developed through self-awareness, effort, and deliberate practice.

Anxiety

Anxiety is defined as an emotion characterized by apprehension and somatic symptoms of tension in which an individual anticipates impending danger, catastrophe, or misfortune (APA Dictionary of Psychology, n.d.). Moreover, anxiety is linked to fear and manifests as a future-oriented mood state that consists of a complex cognitive, affective, physiological, and behavioral response system associated with preparation for the anticipated events or circumstances perceived as threatening (Chand, 2023). Furthermore, according to Ajmal and Ahmad (2019), anxiety is a basic human emotion that consists of fear and uncertainty and usually it occurs when an individual believes that the event is a threat to self or self-esteem and blocks the normal thought process.

In addition, anxiety disorders manifest through an excess of fear and concern, accompanied by related disruptions in behavior. There are several different kinds of anxiety disorders, such as: generalized anxiety disorder (characterized by excessive worry), panic disorder (characterized by panic attacks), social anxiety disorder (characterized by excessive fear and worry in social situations), separation anxiety disorder (characterized by excessive fear or anxiety about separation from those individuals to whom the person has a deep emotional bond), and others (WHO, 2022).

Moreover, anxiety disorders affect around 3.6% of the global population, or over 264 million people, according to the WHO (2022). Another report from the WHO (2022), in 2019, about 301 million people were living with anxiety disorder including 58 million children and adolescents. Anxiety affects 4.6% of females and 2.6% of males worldwide. Anxiety disorders are characterized by repeated intrusive thoughts or concerns. Physical symptoms may include sweating, shaking, disorientation, or a fast pulse. Anxiety and fear are not synonymous, yet they are frequently used interchangeably. Fear is an acceptable, present-oriented, and short-lived response to an identified threat, whereas anxiety is a future-oriented, long-acting response largely centered on a diffuse threat (APA Dictionary of Psychology, n.d.).

Correspondingly, based on Generalized Anxiety Disorder 7 (GAD-7), there are four levels of anxiety, simply divided into minimal, mild, moderate, and severe. With minimal anxiety (0-4), it explains that scores in this range indicate that the individual experiences minimal anxiety symptoms. They may have occasional mild worries or nervousness, but it does not significantly impact their daily functioning or overall well-being. Second is mild anxiety (5-9), which is when individuals with scores falling within this range exhibit mild levels of anxiety. They may experience some persistent worry or nervousness that is noticeable but still manageable. It may start to affect their concentration or ability to relax. The third is moderate anxiety (10-14), which is when scores in this range suggest moderate levels of anxiety. Individuals may frequently experience excessive worry, restlessness, and difficulties controlling their anxiety. These symptoms may start to interfere with their daily activities, productivity, and overall quality of life. Lastly, severe anxiety (15-21) states that scores falling within this range indicate severe levels of anxiety. Individuals may experience intense and persistent worry, restlessness, irritability, and other physical symptoms associated with anxiety, such as muscle tension or trouble sleeping. Their anxiety may significantly impair their ability to function in various areas of life, including work, relationships, and self-care.

There are also factors affecting the student's anxiety such as trauma, stress, social media, COVID-19, and others (Anxiety Disorders - Symptoms and Causes, 2018). Social media platforms often promote a culture of comparison, where individuals compare their lives, achievements, and appearance to others. This constant exposure to carefully curated and idealized versions of others' lives can lead to feelings of inadequacy, low self-esteem, and anxiety. Online platforms can be breeding grounds for cyberbullying, harassment, and negative interactions. Experiencing or witnessing such negative behavior can cause anxiety, stress, and fear associated with using social media. Influencers on social media often portray a lifestyle that is aspirational and unattainable for many. The constant exposure to these unrealistic standards can create pressure to meet such ideals, leading to anxiety, self-comparison, and feelings of inadequacy.

Furthermore, during COVID-19, online learning has been implemented to continue the learners' studies. However, this long-term closing of schools and home quarantine causes negative effects on the physical and mental health of young people. These resulted in anxiety and loneliness in young people (Kılınçel et al., 2021).

Psychological Well-Being

Psychological well-being (PWB) is described as one's degree of psychological happiness and health, which includes emotions of accomplishment and life satisfaction (Madhu et al., 2021). This refers to the individual's overall state of emotional, mental and social well-being which is associated with life experiences. Y. Tang et al. (2019) defined psychological well-being as a core feature of mental health which comprised both hedonic and "eudaimonic", as well as resilience. Hedonic mainly focuses on enjoyment and attainment of pleasure while "eudaimonic" focuses on meaning and life fulfillment. On the other hand, resilience signifies coping, emotion management, and healthy problem resolution. This suggests a high quality of life and efficient functioning.

The Ryff Scales of Psychological Well-Being focuses on measuring multiple facets of psychological well-being including self-acceptance, the establishment of quality ties to others, a sense of autonomy in thought and action, the ability to manage complex environments to suit personal needs and values, the pursuit of meaningful goals, and a sense of purpose in life, continued growth and development as a person. A high total score indicates that the respondent has a mastery of that area in his or her life. Conversely, a low total score shows that the respondent struggles to feel comfortable with that particular concept (Seifert, 2005).

Additionally, people with high psychological well-being report feeling capable, happy, well-supported, and satisfied with life. It shows

that an individual is emotionally stable and functions effectively. According to Kubzansky et al. (2018), people with higher psychological well-being are more likely to live healthier and longer lives as well as enjoy a better quality of life. Moreover, fewer social problems are associated with positive and better psychological well-being. Research has found that people with high psychological well-being are less likely to engage in criminal activity or abuse drugs and alcohol (Morris, 2022). However, psychological well-being is compromised when negative emotions are intense, persistent, and interfere with one's ability to function in daily life.

Psychological well-being is influenced by factors such as past experience and underlying personality. Exposure to different circumstances can have a significant impact on people. Adversity and everyday experiences help individuals build resilience and maintain stable well-being that makes them more capable of coping with various situations. However, experiencing stress and other negative emotions for a long time will result in serious health illnesses and poor performance. Zhuang-Shuang and Hasson (2020) witnessed that persistent exposure to stress could be harmful to individuals' psychological well-being and could negatively affect their satisfaction with their lives and overall quality of life.

Currently, it is known that well-being is dynamic and influenced by personal and cultural variables (King et al., 2014). Psychological well-being is associated with gender, socioeconomic status, birth order, and academic standing. Moreover, the pandemic and social media have significant effects on the psychological well-being of individuals.

The COVID-19 pandemic has had a substantial psychological impact on the world population, and its effects on general mental health are raising increasing concerns (Stufano et al., 2020). The policies adopted by governance, such as social distancing and lockdown measures, can cause social isolation and loneliness which are known to decrease well-being and increase the risk of depression (Stufano et al., 2022). Among COVID-19 stressors, financial instability, unpredictability toward future or career, and media exposure have been described as common factors that cause poor psychological well-being and weaken economic sustainability. It also primarily weakens university students' mental health (Li et al., 2021).

Furthermore, social media has been increasingly used worldwide. It is being considered nowadays as an important part of one's life which enables them to communicate and be informed about various current events. Although moderate use of social media does not interfere with overall functioning and psychological well-being (Twigg et al., 2020), excessive and problematic usage causes serious negative effects. Research investigating the negative outcomes of social media usage has indicated that problematic social media use may lead to deteriorated psychological well-being and overall health.

To date, little research has sought to discover the relationship between students' mindset, their levels of anxiety, and their level of psychological well-being. In the study conducted by Racela et al. (2022), only the students from the Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) strand were studied. There is also insufficient evidence to support that mindset is a determinant of anxiety and anxiety is a determinant of psychological well-being. With this, the researchers would like to further conduct the study with a larger sample size to better assess whether there is a relationship between mindset and anxiety, and anxiety and psychological well-being.

Therefore, this study aims to determine the relationship among mindset, anxiety, and psychological well-being of senior high school students at Saint Mary's University. It is for this purpose that the researchers are prompted to determine the predominated mindset, the level of anxiety, and the level of psychological well-being of the students. The results of this study may serve as a basis for the school's administration to implement interventions and programs that could help the students to improve their overall well-being.

Research Questions

This study aims to determine the relationship among mindset, anxiety, and psychological well-being of senior high school students at Saint Mary's University. Specifically, it seeks answers to the following problems:

1. What are the respondents' predominated mindsets (fixed or growth)?
2. What is the level of anxiety of the respondents?
3. What is the level of psychological well-being of the respondents?
4. Is there a significant difference in the respondents' mindset in terms of the different variables:
 - 4.1. sex;
 - 4.2. strand;
 - 4.3. socioeconomic status;
 - 4.4. birth order; and
 - 4.5. academic standing?
5. Is there a significant difference in the respondents' level of anxiety in terms of the different variables:
 - 5.1. sex;
 - 5.2. strand;
 - 5.3. socioeconomic status
 - 5.4. birth order; and
 - 5.5. academic standing?
6. Is there a significant difference in the level of psychological well-being in terms of the different variables:

- 6.1. sex;
- 6.2. strand;
- 6.3. socioeconomic status;
- 6.4. birth order; an
- 6.5. academic standing?
7. Is there a significant relationship between the respondents' mindset and anxiety?
8. Is there a significant relationship between the respondents' mindset and psychological well-being?
9. Is there a significant relationship between the respondents' anxiety and psychological well-being?
10. What factors affect the respondents' psychological well-being?
11. What activities do the respondents engage in to improve their state of mental health?

Methodology

Research Design

The purpose of this study was to investigate the relationship between mindset, anxiety, and psychological well-being among senior high school students from Saint Mary's University, using a cross-sectional research design with a focus on descriptive- comparative-correlational data collection methods. The study utilized a descriptive research design to explore and determine the respondents' type of mindset, level of anxiety, and level of psychological well-being. Additionally, a comparative research design was used to compare the respondents' mindset, anxiety, and psychological well-being among the different variables. Moreover, a correlational research design was employed to determine the relationship between the respondents' mindset, anxiety, and psychological well-being. Furthermore, the phenomenological design was used to examine the meaning behind the collected data from the open-ended questions in the questionnaire, as well as any other relevant qualitative data that arose during the research process. This method allowed the researchers to identify patterns and themes that emerge from the participants' experiences with mindset, anxiety, and psychological well-being. The results of this study provide insights into the relationship between mindset, anxiety, and psychological well-being among senior high school students, which could inform interventions and programs aimed at promoting mental health and well-being in this population

Participants

Table 1. *Demographic Profile of Respondents*

Variable	f	%
Sex		
Male	212	41.7
Female	296	58.3
Total	508	100.0
Strand		
HUMSS	103	20.3
STEM	260	52.2
ABM	77	15.2
ICT	24	4.7
HE	24	4.7
AD	20	3.9
Total	508	100.0
Socioeconomic Status		
Poor (Less than 9,100)	65	12.8
Low Income (9,100 - 18,200)	62	12.2
Lower Middle (18,200 - 36,400)	128	25.2
Middle (36,400 - 63,700)	110	21.7
Upper Middle (63,700 - 109,200)	82	16.1
High (109,200 and above)	61	12.0
Total	508	100.0
Birth Order		
Oldest	133	26.2
Middle	113	22.2
Youngest	180	35.4
Only Child	77	15.2
Others	5	1.0
Total	508	100.0
Academic Standing		
With Honor	242	47.6
With High Honor	60	11.8
With Highest Honor	19	3.7
Non- Honors	187	36.8
Total	508	100

Legend: Frequency (f); Percentage (%)

The study considered the grade 11 and grade 12 students at the Senior High School Department of Saint Mary's University as the

respondents in terms of data and information gathering. The total number of respondents in this study was 508. The respondents were selected using the stratified random sampling technique to determine the respondents from various strands and tracks that the school offers, including the Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) strand which has 260 respondents, Accountancy, Business, and Management (ABM) strand which has 77 respondents, Humanities and Social Sciences (HUMSS) strand which has 103 respondents, Technical, Vocational, and Livelihood - Information and Communications Technology (TVL-ICT) which has 24 respondents, Home Economics (HE) which has 24 respondents also, and Arts and Design (AD) track which has 20 respondents. Demographic and other factors, such as type of mindset, level of anxiety, and level of psychological well-being, are highlighted and considered key aspects of the research study. Furthermore, a survey questionnaire was distributed to the respondents for data gathering physically per section.

The table shows the frequency count and percentage distribution of demographic profile of the respondents from Saint Mary's University Senior High School. As shown in the table, there are 212 (41.7%) male respondents and 296 (58.3%) female respondents. This means that there are more female respondents than male. Out of 508 respondents, there are 103 (20.3%) HUMSS students 260 (52.2%) STEM students, 77 (15.2%) ABM students, 24 (4.7%) ICT and HE students, and lastly 20 (3.9%) AD students. This reveals that the majority of the respondents are in STEM strand with more than half of the percentage. To classify the socio-economic status of the respondents' base on the monthly income of their parents, the researchers made use the study of Albert et al., (2018).

According to the table, students belonging to the lower middle class whose parents' monthly income is 18,200-36,400 gained the highest frequency which is 128 (25.2%), followed by middle class with monthly income of 36,400-63,700 which is 110 (21.7%). This means that the socioeconomic status of the majority of the students is in the middle. The table further shows that 133 (26.2%) of the respondents are the oldest in their family, 113 (22.2%) are middle, 180 (35.4%) are the youngest in their family, 77 (15.2%) are the only child in their family and 5 (1.0%) of them are born third, fourth and fifth. This means that there is a more significant number of young respondents. Lastly, the table presents that 242 (47.6%) of the respondents are With Honor, 60 (11.8%) With High Honors, 19 (3.7%) are With Highest Honors and 187 (36.8%) of the respondents who arenon-honors. This reveals that most of the respondents have academic standing, most especially With Honor.

Instruments

The researchers used a modified survey questionnaire to gather data on the type of mindset, level of anxiety, and level of psychological well-being of the respondents. The questionnaire that will be utilized in this study was adapted from the research of Racela et al. (2022), entitled "Mindset, Anxiety, and Psychological Well-Being of Senior High School (STEM) Students." The questionnaire is comprised of three (3) parts, including the socio-demographic profile of respondents, a quantitative section wherein the Likert scale will be used, and a qualitative section wherein two (2) open-ended questions will be asked to the respondents.

The socio-demographic profile of the respondents was collected in the first part of the questionnaire. Personal information questions were asked, including the respondent's name (optional), sex, strand, monthly income of parents, birth order, and academic standing.

The second part of the questionnaire aims to gather quantitative responses from the participants. This part consists of three (3) tests: a mindset quiz, an anxiety test, and a psychological well-being test. The Mindset Quiz is a 9-item test adapted from Carol S. Dweck (2006) and it is designed to determine whether the respondent has a fixed or growth mindset. It is a 4-point Likert scale questionnaire with label 1 as strongly disagree, 2 as disagree, 3 as agree, and 4 as strongly agree. The GAD-7 Anxiety Test is a 7-item test developed by Spitzer et al. (2006) and it is used as a screening tool and severity measure for generalized anxiety disorder. It is a 4-point Likert scale test with labels 0 as not at all, 1 as several days, 2 as more than half the day, and 3 as nearly every day. The psychological well-being test was developed by Carol Ryff (1989). The test is designed to measure the level of psychological well-being of respondents. It is made up of 16-item statements where one is asked to describe their agreement or disagreement on a 4-point Likert scale.

Meanwhile, the third part sought to collect qualitative responses, wherein two (2) questions were answered openly by the respondents of the study.

Result of Reliability Test

Table 2. *Result of Reliability Test for Mindset Quiz*

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of items
.775	.796	9

Table 3. *Result of Reliability Test for Anxiety Test*

Cronbach's Alpha	N of items
.873	7

Table 4. *Result of Reliability Test for Psychological Well-Being Test*

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of items
.917	.922	18

The tables show the result of the reliability statistics. Based on Table 1, Cronbach's alpha is equal to 0.775. Its internal consistency is equivalent to acceptable ($0.8 > \alpha \geq 0.7$). Moreover, according to the results of Table 2, the Cronbach's alpha is equal to 0.873. Its internal consistency is equivalent to good ($0.9 > \alpha \geq 0.8$). Furthermore, according to the results of Table 3, the Cronbach's alpha is equal to 0.917. Its internal consistency is equivalent to excellent ($\alpha \geq 0.9$). Therefore, the questionnaire is reliable.

Procedure

The study's data gathering procedure begins with the modification of the adapted research questionnaire. The adapted research questionnaires are the GAD-7 anxiety test, the mindset quiz, which was adapted from Carol Dweck (2006), and the psychological well-being test, which was adapted from the developed questionnaire of Carol Ryff (1989). After such, the research questionnaire was validated by the research adviser, research coordinators, and research teacher. Upon the validation of questionnaire, the researchers secured permission to conduct the study from the office of the principal. The researchers then conducted a pilot testing prior to the actual data collection to check the validity of the questions. Next, the retrieval of data was employed. Afterwards, the researchers tested the reliability of the questionnaires by using the SPSS application. Once the questionnaire is found reliable, the researchers proceeded in administering the questionnaires personally to the target respondents of the study. The collection of data from the senior high school students at Saint Mary's University were employed. The data was then presented using tables. Finally, the tabulated data was analyzed and interpreted to draw conclusions and recommendations.

Data Analysis

This study utilized a descriptive-comparative-correlational research design to address the research questions. Hence, to treat the data gathered, the following tools and techniques will be used:

The frequency count and percentage distribution were used to determine the respondents' demographic profile and the respondents' levels of anxiety.

Mean score and standard deviation were computed to determine the types of mindsets, and levels of psychological well-being of the students at Saint Mary's University Senior High School. An equal interval was also utilized since this type of scale produces a more reliable and valid analysis. Therefore, the mean score for each descriptor is interpreted using the following systems:

Table 5. *Likert Scale Interpretation for Mindset*

Mean Range	Qualitative Description
3.50- 4.00	Strong Growth Mindset
2.50-3.49	Growth mindset with some fix ideas
1.50-2.49	Fix mindset with some growth ideas
1.00-1.49	Strong Fix Mindset

Table 6. *Likert Scale Interpretation for Anxiety*

Score	Qualitative Description
15-21	Severe Anxiety
10-14	Moderate Anxiety
5-9	Mild Anxiety
0-4	Minimal Anxiety

Table 7. *Likert Scale Interpretation for Psychological Well-Being*

Mean Range	Qualitative Description
3.50- 4.00	Very High Psychological Well-being
2.50-3.49	High Psychological Well-being
1.50-2.49	Low Psychological Well-being
1.00-1.49	Very Low Psychological Well-being

The independent samples T-test was used to determine the significant difference between the two-variable sex on the Mindset, Anxiety, and Psychological Well-being of Senior High School students. One-way ANOVA was used to determine the significant difference in the strand, monthly income of parents, birth order, and academic standing on the Mindset, Anxiety, and Psychological Well-being of senior high school students.

The Pearson r correlation was used to determine the relationship between the respondent's mindset and anxiety, the respondent's mindset and psychological well-being, and the respondent's anxiety and psychological well-being.

Thematic analysis is the most appropriate in understanding the factors that affect the respondents' psychological well-being and activities that they engage in to improve their state of mental health across a data set. Thematic analysis assisted in the creation of themes or meanings disguised as patterns derived from data gathering that address the research topic (Kiger & Varpio, 2020). Thus, thematic analysis will be employed to further understand and analyze the qualitative responses of the respondents

Ethical Considerations

This research paper signifies that this study's purpose was to determine the relationship between mindset, anxiety, and psychological well-being of the senior high school students at Saint Mary's University in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the subject Practical Research. The researchers considered the sections under ethical consideration that were applicable to the study. The following sections were as follows:

Informed Consent

To ensure that participants understand the study, the researchers provided them with consent forms. These forms explained the purpose of the study and state that the participants have the right to refuse or participate in the study. The forms also specify the boundaries of confidentiality of the study, which means that the information collected from the participants will be kept private.

Confidentiality and Data Protection

If the participants decide to participate in the study, the researchers used anonymous data whenever possible, which means that no identifying information was collected, and respondents cannot be identified. Since the study collected data from the respondents, the following steps will be followed to properly handle the collected data.

Storage- All the gathered data was stored securely, both during and after the research process and there was limited access for those who needed it.

Sharing- The researchers were the only ones who had access to the data collected and ensured that all data sharing was done in accordance with legal and ethical guidelines.

Disposal- To dispose of the data securely once it is no longer needed, the researchers used methods such as shredding of data and deleting an electronic file that was collected.

Risk / Benefit Ratio

The data discovered during the research procedure might be used to present evidence to the guidance office of the school, which may pose a potential risk to the confidentiality of the respondents. To avoid breaking any rules during this process, the researchers will adhere to the Marian Ethics Board. However, after analyzing the results of this study, the results will be given to the guidance office of the university and to the administration of the school as well, in order for the school to implement interventions and programs that may help the students to improve their overall well-being.

Conflict of interest

There was no conflict of interest in this study since none of the researchers or other people will have personal financial gain. Also, the results and knowledge that was gained in this study benefited a lot of people, especially the Senior High School students from Saint Mary's University.

Management of Vulnerability

The purpose of this research was to know the relationship between Mindset, Anxiety, and Psychological Well-being of Saint Mary's University Senior High School students. The vulnerability of students who participated in this study was high which implies that their information was protected properly and maintained confidentiality.

The research questionnaire has been submitted to the office of the Guidance Counselor and has later been approved. The reason for this was to make sure that the questions will not trigger any case of mental health issues and to make sure that the respondents were safe from emotional harm.

Assuming that the participants or respondents feel that their privacy was not being respected, the researchers may give their contact information to them, or they may call the guidance office.

In conclusion, this study recognized the importance of sustaining ethical standards and protecting the rights and well-being of vulnerable respondents participating in this study. The researchers were committed to conducting this research in a manner that respects the freedom, dignity, rights of all respondents, and ensuring that they were not exploited in any way.

Results and Discussion

This section focuses on the presentation, analysis, and interpretation of data gathered from the respondents. The results of statistical analysis are presented in tabulated form and interpreted based on the scale interpretation. This discusses the level of mindset, anxiety,

and psychological well-being of Saint Mary's University Senior High School students, the significant differences on the type of mindset, anxiety, and psychological well-being when grouped according to the different profile variables, and the relationships between mindset and anxiety, mindset and psychological well-being, and anxiety and psychological well-being.

Level of Mindset, Anxiety, and Psychological Well-Being of Saint Mary's University Senior High School

Table 8. *Level of Respondents' Mindset*

Statements	Mean	SD	Description
1. Your intelligence is something very basic about you that you can change very much.	2.91	.732	Growth mindset with some fixed ideas
2. No matter how much intelligence you have, you can always change it quite a bit.	3.05	.621	Growth mindset with some fixed ideas
3. The harder you work at something, the better you will be.	3.13	.750	Growth mindset with some fixed ideas
4. People can be truly good at sports, you don't have to be born with the ability.	3.48	.654	Growth mindset with some fixed ideas
5. I often get motivated when I get feedback about my performance.	3.32	.719	Growth mindset with some fixed ideas
6. I appreciate when people, parents, coaches, or teachers give me feedback about my performance.	3.38	.719	Growth mindset with some fixed ideas
7. You can always change how intelligent you are.	3.09	.740	Growth mindset with some fixed ideas
8. You are a certain kind of person and there's still much that can be done to really change that.	3.25	.663	Growth mindset with some fixed ideas
Overall Mean	3.21	.439	Growth mindset with some fixed ideas

Legend: Standard Deviation (SD); Strong Fix Mindset (1.00-1.49); Fix mindset with some growth ideas (1.50- 2.49); Growth mindset with some fix ideas (2.50-3.49); Strong Growth Mindset (3.50-4.00)

Table 8 shows that Saint Mary's University senior high school students have a growth mindset with some fixed ideas with an overall mean of 3.21. Students agreed that "People can be truly good at sports; you don't have to be born with the ability." which acquired the highest mean of 3.48 indicating growth mindset with some fixed ideas. However, the Statement 1 gained the lowest mean of 2.91 which also indicates growth mindset with some fixed ideas. This implies that the students at Saint Mary's University Senior High School commonly hold the belief that hard work, intense dedication, steadfast determination and open-mindedness are all necessary for one to improve mental abilities and attain proficiency in a certain field. Romero (2015) also states that intelligence can be developed through hard work, the use of effective strategies, and help from others when needed.

Table 9. *Respondents' Level of Anxiety*

	f	%
Severe (15-21)	175	34.45
Moderate (10-14)	184	36.22
Mild (5-9)	107	21.06
Minimal (0-4)	42	8.27
Total	508	100.0

Table 9 presents the level of anxiety of the senior high school students. According to the table presented, most of the students have moderate anxiety with a frequency of 184 (36.22%), followed by severe anxiety with a frequency of 175 (34.45%), followed by mild anxiety with a frequency of 107 (21.065) and minimal anxiety has the lowest frequency with 42 (8.27%). It appears that the students are experiencing moderate to severe anxiety and may frequently experience symptoms of excessive worry, restlessness, and difficulties controlling their anxiety. In the study by Sahin and Tuna (2022), students were also found to have moderate level of anxiety. Moreover, they state that moderate anxiety had a negative and significant effect on thriving and its subdimensions of vitality and learning.

Table 10 shows that senior high school students have high psychological well-being with an overall mean of 2.93. Students perceived that "Life has a continuous process of learning, changing, and growth" which acquired the highest mean of 3.37 indicating a high psychological well-being. The rest of the statements also fall under high psychological well-being. This implies that students with high psychological well-being feel capable, happy, well-supported, and satisfied with life. It also shows that an individual is emotionally stable and functions effectively. The study conducted by Multisari et al. (2022) found that students with high psychological well-being were likelier to report feeling capable, happy, and well-supported. They were also more likely to report being satisfied with their lives and functioning academically and personally.

Table 10. Respondents' Level of Psychological Well-Being

Statements	Mean	SD	Description
1. I like most parts of my personality.	2.81	.7767	High
2. When I look at the story of my life, I am pleased with how things have turned out so far.	2.87	.8005	High
3. For me, life has been a continuous process of learning, changing, and growth.	3.37	.6911	High
4. I am not afraid to voice my opinions, even when they are in opposition to the opinions of most people.	2.79	.8205	High
5. I enjoy making plans for the future and working to make them a reality.	3.16	.6785	High
6. I think it is important to have new experiences that challenge how you think about yourself and the world.	3.34	.6766	High
7. Most people see me as loving and affectionate.	2.71	.8141	High
9. In general, I feel I am in charge of the situation in which I live.	2.97	.7649	High
10. I am good at managing the responsibilities of daily life.	2.73	.7920	High
11. I sometimes feel as I've done all there is to do in life	2.55	.9421	High
12. People would describe me as a giving person, willing to share my time with others.	2.94	.7522	High
13. I gave up trying to make big improvements or changes in my life a long time ago.	2.54	.9359	High
14. I tend to be influenced by people with strong opinions.	2.97	.7710	High
15. I know that I can trust my friends, and they know they can trust me.	3.12	.7330	High
16. I have confidence in my own opinions, even if they are different from the way most other people think	2.92	.7622	High
17. I enjoy personal and mutual conversations with family members and friends	3.17	.7353	High
Overall Mean	2.93	.436	High

Legend: Standard Deviation (SD); Very Low PWB (1.00-1.49); Low PWB (1.50-2.49); High PWB(2.50-3.49); Very High PWB (3.50-4.00)

Significant Difference on the Respondents' Level of Mindset in terms of the Different Profile Variables

Table 11. Significant Difference on the Level of Mindset when Grouped according to their Sex

	Groups	N	Mean	SD	t-value	p-value
Level of Mindset	Male	212	3.23	.423	1.093*	.275
	Female	296	3.19	.450		

*p > 0.05 Legend: Population (N); Standard Deviation (SD)

Table 11 shows the results of independent sample T-test on significant difference on the level of mindset of Saint Mary's University senior high school students in terms of sex. As can be seen, the computed p-value is higher than the level of significance, which is 0.05, so the null hypothesis is accepted. Hence, there is no significant difference between mindset and sex (p=.275). As illustrated also in the table, the mean of the level of mindset of males (Mean=3.23) is higher that of females (Mean=3.19). However, both sexes still fall under the category of growth mindset with some fixed ideas. While there are structural differences observed between the brains of men and women, these differences do not lead to variations within the mindset of each sex. These differences do not affect the cognitive abilities and behaviors of individuals, which elicit the belief that men are better than women. Mindset is far more influenced by the person's environment and unique experiences than by sex. Regardless of sex, the thoughts, beliefs, and behaviors of individuals are continuously shaped by various factors such as personal, social, and environmental. In the study conducted by Tao et al. (2022), it was also found that there is no significant difference between sex and mindset. This suggests that sex does not play a role in determining whether one will have a growth mindset or fixed mindset.

Table 12. Significant Difference on the Type of Mindset when Grouped according to their Strand

	Groups	N	Mean	SD	F-value	p-value
Level of Mindset	HUMSS	103	3.26	.33	1.029*	.400
	STEM	260	3.19	.49		
	ABM	77	3.26	.43		
	ICT	24	3.10	.51		
	HE	24	3.15	.32		
	AD	20	3.17	.34		

*p > 0.05

Table 12 presents the analysis of variance (ANOVA) results on the level of mindset when respondents were grouped according to the different variables. In terms of strand, the table shows that there is no significant difference on the level of mindset among senior high school students ($F=1.029$; $p=.400$). This implies that the strand is not a determinant of mindset. The choice of strand can significantly influence the student’s skills and knowledge into a certain field that suits their interest and goals, but it does not significantly alter their beliefs and attitudes. As one is determined to work hard and dedicated to learning, students will have the potential to foster growth mindset and be successful, regardless of their strand. They will encounter and engage into new experiences, teachers, subjects and other circumstances, especially as they progress in education which develop new perspectives that affects their mindset (Limeri et al., 2020). It is important to note that the educational environment is what influence one’s mindset and not the strand itself.

Table 13. Significant Difference on the Level of Mindset when Grouped according to their Socioeconomic Status

	Groups	N	Mean	SD	F-value	p-value
Level of Mindset	Poor	65	3.16	.38	1.769*	.118
	Low-income	62	3.27	.49		
	Low Middle	128	3.17	.42		
	Middle	110	3.21	.38		
	Upper Middle	82	3.17	.45		
	High	61	3.33	.54		

* $p > 0.05$

Table 13 reveals that there is no significant difference on the level of mindset of senior high school students and the monthly income of their parents ($F=1.769$, $p=.118$). There is insufficient evidence to conclude in this study that mindset is determined based on socioeconomic status. Being rich does not mean a higher level of mindset and being poor does not equate to having a fixed mindset. With strong perseverance, people from any socioeconomic background can develop a growth mindset. Socioeconomic status may not directly influence the mindset however, it is important to note that it may still cause the occurrence of circumstances that make it difficult for students to improve their cognitive abilities, set of beliefs and attitudes, especially those from lower socioeconomic status. The result contradicts the study of Destin et al. (2019) wherein it presents that those individual with higher socioeconomic status has less of a fixed mindset than those with lower ones.

Moreover, it states that socioeconomic status might guide the development of students’ broader fixed or growth mindsets in systematic ways with consequences for academic outcomes. The number of students being studied in this research were lower than the study conducted by Destin et al. with two analytic samples - 4,828 main and 2,872 participants. Also, based on the gathered data, most of respondents belong to the middle-class family which results in unequal variations with the other socioeconomic status, which results to contradictory findings.

Table 14. Significant Difference on the Level of Mindset when Grouped according to their Birth Order

	Groups	N	Mean	SD	F-value	p-value
Level of Mindset	Oldest	133	3.21	.44	1.019*	.397
	Middle	113	3.28	.37		
	Youngest	180	3.18	.46		
	Only Child	77	3.17	.49		
	Others	5	3.09	.48		

* $p > 0.05$

Table 14 presents the ANOVA results on the level of mindset when respondents were grouped according to birth order. It shows that there is no significant difference between these two variables ($F=1.019$, $p=.397$). This implies that mindset is not associated with individual’s position among siblings. Students, either first born or later born, may hold beliefs which are largely influenced by external factors such as family, parenting styles, social, and environmental. There is no sufficient proof that first born will more likely to have higher level of mindset than later born. Similar results were found in the study of Stannard et al., (2019) wherein they stated that they did not found evidence to find the significant different between the two variables.

Table 15. Significant Difference on the Level of Mindset when Grouped according to their Academic Standing

	Groups	N	Mean	SD	F-value	p-value
Level of Mindset	With Honors	242	3.24 ^A	.44	4.343**	.005
	With High Honors	60	3.32 ^B	.45		
	With Highest Honors	19	3.31	.44		
	Non-Honors	187	3.13 ^{AB}	.42		

* $p > 0.05$. Mean groups who share a common letter are significantly different from each other

Table 15 indicates that there is a significant difference on the level of mindset when the respondents are grouped according to their academic standing ($F=4.343$, $p=.005$). This implies that one’s mindset can significantly impact their academic performance. Students with growth mindset believe that they can improve their capabilities by exerting effort, learning and persevering and are known to perform better academically. They are able to manage their studies well which allows them to reach their goals and use failure and

setbacks as opportunities for improvement. The study conducted by Limeri et al. (2020) corroborate this result and further implies that mindset and academic performance constitute a positive feedback loop.

As shown in the table, the academic standing that attained a p-value of less than .05 are between With Honor and Non-academic achiever ($p=.045$) and With High Honor and Non-Honors ($p=.012$). This means that the Study identified a significant difference for students categorized by their level (With Honors, With High Honors, With Highest Honors, and Without Academic Distinction). This also implies that the mindset of students with academic standing is better than those who were non-academic achievers. They are dedicated to their learning and have strong determination that allows them to nurture their mind and improve themselves. However, the table shows no significant difference between With Highest Honor and without academic distinction. This might be due to the lower number of respondents whose academic standing is With Highest Honor. The result of this study is consistent with other research findings. The 2018 study from the Program for International Student Assessment (PISA) found that students with a growth mindset performed dramatically better than those with fixed mindset. It can be seen also in the table that students with no academic standing gained negative mean differences. This indicates that they have a fixed mindset.

Significant Difference on the Respondents' Level of Anxiety in terms of the Different Variables

Table 16. *Significant Difference on the Level of Anxiety when Grouped According to their Sex*

	Groups	N	Score	SD	t-value	p-value
Level of Anxiety	Male	212	11.34	5.08	-3.418**	.001
	Female	296	12.93	5.24		

** $p < 0.05$ Legend: Population (N); Standard Deviation (SD); Minimal (0-4); Mild (5-9); Moderate (10-14); Severe (15-21)

Table 16 shows the significant difference on the level of anxiety when respondents are group in terms of sex. Both male and female have moderate level of anxiety with scores of 11.34 and 12.93, respectively. This signifies that students frequently experience excessive worry, restlessness, and difficulties which may due to various factor such as academics and environment. As seen also in the table, there is a significant difference between the level of anxiety and sex ($p=.001$). This indicates that anxiety level can be determined based on the sex of an individual which is similar with the findings in the study of Naceanceno et al. (2021). Women are more likely to experience than men due to different factors that can trigger anxiety including hormonal changes and particular life events. In the 2017 study conducted by McLean et al., it was found that women were twice as likely to be diagnosed with an anxiety disorder as men. This is also similar with the findings of this study as it can be seen in the table that the anxiety score of female is slightly greater than male, suggesting that female are more likely to experience this mental health condition.

Table 17. *Significant Difference on the Level of Respondents' Anxiety when Grouped According to Strand*

	Groups	N	Score	SD	F-value	p-value
Level of Anxiety	HUMSS	103	13.18	.72	3.216**	.007
	STEM	260	11.48	.74		
	ABM	77	12.44	.82		
	ICT	24	13.58	.61		
	HE	24	14.63	.58		
	AD	20	12.75	.81		

** $p < 0.05$

Table 17 presents the ANOVA result on the level of anxiety when the senior high school students were grouped in terms of strand. According to the table, there is a significant difference on the level of anxiety when respondents are grouped according to their strand ($F=3.216$; $p = 0.007$). Same results were also found in the study of Bustillo et al. (2019) and Amanullah et al. (2008). This shows that the level of anxiety could vary from one strand to another (Bustillo et al., 2019).

However, while a one-way ANOVA showed a significant difference, multiple comparisons test yielded no significant difference among the six strands. It can be inferred that there is a large difference between the strands.

Table 18. *Significant Difference on the Level of Respondents' Anxiety when Grouped According to their Socioeconomic Status*

	Groups	N	Score	SD	F-value	p-value
Level of Anxiety	Poor	65	11.52	.77	1.690*	.135
	Low-income	62	12.92	.70		
	Low Middle	128	11.79	.71		
	Middle	110	12.80	.64		
	Upper Middle	82	13.09	.83		
	High	61	11.34	.87		

* $p > 0.05$

Table 18 shows that there is no significant difference in the level of anxiety of respondents when grouped according to socioeconomic status ($F=1.690$; $p = .135$). This indicates that regardless of socioeconomic status, the level of anxiety of an individual can possibly

experience minimal to severe anxiety depending on the impact of the social, economic and other external factors in their lives. This contradicts the study conducted by Zhu et al. (2019) wherein they found that lower SES was associated with higher levels of anxiety symptoms in adolescents. The discrepancy might be due to the cultural differences as the participants involved in the study of Zhu et al. are Chinese adolescents.

Table 19. *Significant Difference on the Level of Respondents' Anxiety when Grouped According to their Birth Order*

	Groups	N	Score	SD	F-value	p-value
Level of Anxiety	Oldest	133	11.83	.78	1.642*	.162
	Middle	113	12.67	.73		
	Youngest	180	12.00	.73		
	Only Child	77	12.77	.74		
	Others	5	16.80	1.05		

* $p > 0.05$. Mean groups who share a common letter are significantly different from each other

Table 19 presents that there is no significant difference on the level of anxiety. ($F=1.642$; $p=.162$). This implies that regardless of being born first or last, the anxiety level will mostly base on the experience with family including the pressure they are putting on them. This refutes the study that shows firstborns reported lower levels of anxiety compared to later-borns which is conducted by Furnham and Cheng (2021).

Table 20. *Significant Difference on the Level of Respondents' Anxiety when Grouped According to their Academic Standing*

	Groups	N	Mean	SD	F-value	p-value
Level of Anxiety	With Honors	242	11.64	.79	2.384*	.069
	With High Honors	60	12.70	.72		
	With Highest Honors	19	13.53	.84		
	Non-Honors	187	12.82	.68		

* $p > 0.05$

Table 20 shows the ANOVA result on the level of anxiety when respondents were grouped according to their academic standing. The table reveals that there is no significant difference between anxiety and academic standing ($F=2.384$, $p = .069$). This means that students may have a high level of anxiety but are still able to perform well or succeed academically. They may be also likely to lose focus and motivation leading to low academic performance. In a blog published by the International Board of Credentialing and Continuing Education Standards (IBCCES 2020), it states that anxiety negatively influence academic performance of students whereas, students with a high level of anxiety score lower on IQ and achievement tests than their peers. In the study conducted by Malhotra et al.(2013), it also revealed that there is no significant difference in the anxiety level and academic achievement scores of adolescents.

Significant Difference on the Respondents' Level of Psychological Well-Being in terms of the Different Variables

Table 21. *Significant Difference on the Level of Respondents' Psychological Well-Being when Grouped According to their Sex*

	Groups	N	Mean	SD	t-value	p-value
Level of PWB	Male	212	2.95	.488	.879*	.380
	Female	296	2.91	.394		

* $p > 0.05$

Table 21 shows the independent sample t-test on significant difference on the level of anxiety when respondents are group in terms of sex. Based on the result of the independent sample t-test, there is no significant difference between psychological well-being and sex ($p = .380$). The level of psychological well-being of Male (Mean = 2.95) is slightly greater than Female (Mean = 2.91). This implies that sex do not influence the psychological well-being of an individual. This corresponds with the results from the study of Sallah et al. (2016) wherein they found that there were no significant differences in terms of gender and psychological well-being and all the dimensions of psychological well- being including autonomy, environmental mastery, positive relations with others. However, Tao et al. (2020) recent study has demonstrated that gender was a major contributing factor to one's self-rated health and functional well-being.

Table 22. *Significant Difference Between Respondents' Psychological Well-being when Grouped According to their Strand*

	Groups	N	Mean	SD	F-value	p-value
Level of PWB	HUMSS	103	2.95	.42	1.239*	.289
	STEM	260	2.91	.44		
	ABM	77	2.99	.43		
	ICT	24	2.81	.49		
	HE	24	3.03	.48		
	AD	20	2.82	.31		

* $p > 0.05$

Table 22 presents the ANOVA result on the level of psychological well-being when the senior high school students were grouped according to their strand. The table shows that there is no significant difference between psychological well-being and strand ($F=1.239$; $p = .289$). This implies that students from any strand respond well to various factors that influences their psychological well-being. This result is similar with the result of the study conducted by Morales et al (2020) wherein they found no significant differences between strand in relation to psychological well-being since there is no difference between male and female participants in terms of self-acceptance, positive relations with others, autonomy, environmental mastery, purpose in life, and personal growth.

Table 23. *Significant Difference Between Respondents' Psychological Well-being when Grouped According to their Socioeconomic Status*

	Groups	N	Mean	SD	F-value	p-value
Level of PWB	Poor	65	2.83 ^A	.44	2.527**	.028
	Low-income	62	2.97	.50		
	Low Middle	128	2.88	.40		
	Middle	110	2.97	.43		
	Upper Middle	82	2.91	.40		
	High	61	3.06 ^B	.47		

** $p < 0.05$. Mean groups who share a common letter are significantly different from each other

Table 23 shows that there is a significant difference on the level of psychological well-being when respondents are grouped according to the monthly income of their parents ($F=2.527$; $p = 0.028$). This suggests that socioeconomic status has greatly influenced the psychological well-being of students. Children from lower-income families are more likely to experience several negative outcomes, such as lower academic achievement, increased involvement in risky behaviors, and decreased physical health (Ferguson, 2007). Additionally, children from lower-income families are more likely to develop chronic health conditions, such as heart disease and diabetes, in adulthood.

As shown in the table, the monthly income that attained a p -value of less than .05 is between poor income (less than 9100) and high income (109200 and above). It can be seen also in the table that high socioeconomic status (109200 and above) gained positive mean differences whereas poor socioeconomic status (less than 9100) gained negative mean differences. This indicates that the higher the SES, the higher the level of psychological well-being of the respondents. Conversely, the lower the SES, the lower the level of psychological well-being of the respondents.

The results coincide with the 2018 study conducted by Remes et al. (2021) wherein it is found that people with lower incomes were more likely to report symptoms of depression and anxiety. Additionally, Hao and Farah (2020) also found that people from lower SES backgrounds were more likely to experience negative emotions, such as stress and anger.

Table 24. *Difference Between Respondents' Psychological Well-being when Grouped According to their Birth Order*

	Groups	N	Mean	SD	F-value	p-value
Level of PWB	Oldest	133	2.92	.48	.814*	.517
	Middle	113	2.97	.46		
	Youngest	180	2.92	.41		
	Only Child	77	2.91	.38		
	Others	5	2.65	.50		

* $p > 0.05$

Table 24 shows that there is no significant difference on the level of psychological well-being of the respondents in terms of birth order ($F=.814$; $p = .517$). This implies that birth order has no associations with psychological well-being. The individual's experience within family could influence and shape their well-being than birth order alone. This is similar with the findings of Rorher and Egloff (2018) wherein they found that birth order has no effect on extraversion, emotional stability, agreeableness, conscientiousness, or imagination of individual. However, it contradicts the study conducted by Sharma and Srimathi (2014), wherein it was found that personal growth was higher in first-borns than in lower birth orders. In their study, students between 18-43 years which are from various Under Graduate and Post Graduate Colleges were studied. The age range of their respondents is higher compared to our study, leading to conflicting results.

Table 25. *Significant Difference on Respondents' Psychological Well-being and Academic Standing*

	Groups	N	Mean	SD	F-value	p-value
Level of PWB	With Honor	242	2.95	.42	.836*	.475
	With High Honor	60	2.93	.42		
	With Highest Honor	19	3.03	.68		
	Non-Honors	187	2.90	.43		

* $p > 0.05$

Table 25 shows that there is no significant difference on the level of psychological well-being when respondents are grouped according to their academic standing ($F=.836$; $p = .475$). This suggests that students could have psychological well-being issues but are still capable

of perform well in their academics or respond to various problems. This is in contrast with the findings of Mustafa et al. (2020) wherein it was found that there is a significant positive correlation between the dimensions of psychological well-being, such as environmental mastery, personal growth, positive relationships with others, personal goals, self-acceptance, and academic achievement.

While some students can still maintain their academic standings despite of dealing with psychological well-being issues, some students depend on their psychological well-being for them to maintain or achieve their academic standing.

Correlation between Mindset, Anxiety, and Psychological Well-being

Table 26. Significant Relationship Between Mindset and Anxiety

	Pearson's r	p-value	QD
Mindset ↔ Anxiety	.015*	.739	Very Low Positive Correlation

Legend:

Pearson r Qualitative Description +0.40 – +0.59 High Correlation
+0.80 – +0.99 Very High Correlation +0.20 – +0.39 Moderately Low Correlation
+0.60 – +0.79 Moderately High Correlation +0.01 – +0.19 Very Low Correlation
*p>0.05

Table 26 shows the correlation between the respondents' mindset and anxiety. According to the table above, there is no significant relationship between the mindset and anxiety of the respondents ($p=0.739$). Pursuant to the result of Pearson r correlation, which is 0.015, indicates that there is a very low positive correlation between the two variables. This implies that mindset is not determinant of anxiety. The same results were found in the study of Racela et al. (2022) which also found no significant correlation between mindset and anxiety in a sample of 312 STEM respondents. Similar results were also found in the study of Northrop (2014) states that there was no significant relationship between mindset and anxiety of the respondents.

Table 27. Relationship Between Mindset and Psychological Well-Being

	Pearson's r	p-value	QD
Mindset ↔ PWB	.366**	.000	Moderately Low Positive Correlation

Legend:

Pearson r Qualitative Description +0.40 – +0.59 High Correlation
+0.80 – +0.99 Very High Correlation +0.20 – +0.39 Moderately Low Correlation
+0.60 – +0.79 Moderately High Correlation +0.01 – +0.19 Very Low Correlation
**p<0.05

Table 27 shows the correlation between the respondents' mindset and psychological well-being. According to the table above, there is a significant relationship between the respondent's mindset and psychological well-being ($p= 0.00$). Furthermore, the Pearson r correlation coefficient was 0.366 indicating a moderately low positive correlation. This implies that if a student has a good mindset, he or she also have a high psychological well-being or vice versa. According to Zeng (2016), development of high levels of growth mindsets in students predicts higher psychological well-being and school engagement through enhancement of resilience. Furthermore, studies have shown that students with better psychological well-being are more likely to enjoy a better quality of life and good mindset, (Morin, 2022). The same findings were also found in the study of Racela et al. (2022) which stated that there was a significant relationship between the respondents' mindset and psychological well-being.

Table 28. Relationship Between Anxiety and Psychological Well-Being

	Pearson's r	p-value	QD
Mindset ↔ PWB	-.006*	.898	Very Low Negative Correlation

Legend:

Pearson r Qualitative Description +0.40 – +0.59 High Correlation
+0.80 – +0.99 Very High Correlation +0.20 – +0.39 Moderately Low Correlation
+0.60 – +0.79 Moderately High Correlation +0.01 – +0.19 Very Low Correlation
*p>0.05

Table 28 shows the correlation between the respondents' anxiety and psychological well-being. According to the table above, there is no significant relationship between the respondent's anxiety and psychological well-being ($p= .898$). Furthermore, the Pearson r correlation coefficient was -0.006, which means a very low negative correlation. Therefore, anxiety is not determinant of psychological well-being. The same findings were found in the study of Racela et al. (2022) states that there was no significant relationship between anxiety and psychological well-being.

Result of Thematic Analysis

Table 29 presents the factors affecting the psychological well-being of the respondents. According to the table above, the experiences, environment, academics, psychological, and socioeconomic factors affect the student's psychological well-being.

Table 29. *Factors Affecting the Psychological Well-being of Saint Mary's University Senior High School Students*

Factors	Sample Statements	f	%
Experiences	"Bad or negative experiences such as, being bullied, death of a loved one, and other traumas." (1 and 457)	140	27.03
Environment	"Factors such as my environment, like if my environment is full of negative people, I feel like exploding the next second. Like my mind would be full of these weird complexing dark circles and my mind would force me to just and isolate and lock myself inside my room." (76)	179	34.56
Academics	"Stress from school, too much activities that is burning me out. It is also the validation I get from my environment." (357, 170)	52	10.04
Psychological Factors	"The factors that affects my psychological well-being are pressure, fears, criticisms, expectations, experiences, responsibilities and others."(356)	137	26.45
Socio-Economic Factors	"Being problematic about our financial situation affects my psychological well-being." (21)	10	1.93

The respondents' environment is a great contributor that affects the psychological well-being of the respondents, with a total response of 179 (34.56%). The environment the students are surrounded in, such as their family and their peers or friends. One of the respondents stated, "The environment I am currently situated in, whether at home, school, work, etc., affects my psychological well-being because of their opinions and criticisms about my life." Family is the basic unit of the community and the foundation of the community. In the study of Badamas et al. (2023), family plays a significant role on how children develop, and a steady family that is steady on their responsibility and functionality is essential to the development of a child. The family is also the first school for children, and their attitudes reflect what they learn at home. Therefore, a child's home environment should offer a favorable framework for healthy psychological well-being (Badamas et al., 2023).

Another factor that affects the students' psychological well-being is their peers. Peers influence the way they act and think; this may be in the form of peer pressure. In the study of J. Cruz et al. (2022), they found a significant relationship between peer pressure and the psychological well-being of Senior High School students.

Another contributor that affects the students' psychological well-being is their experiences, with a total response of 140 (27.03%). Those experiences are the history of being bullied, past relationships, the death of a loved one, and other traumatic experiences the students experience. According to Mental Health America (n.d.), Trauma negatively impacts young people's sense of self, making it difficult for those students to feel motivated, proud, and engaged in their learning. One of the respondents responded, "Traumas not spoken of relapses due to triggers, certain people that should never be brought up." This implies that traumatic experiences affect the students' psychological well-being.

Moreover, psychological factors are also a great contributor that affect the students' psychological well-being, with a total response of 137(26.45%). These psychological factors include overthinking, fears, stress, pressure, anxiety, and depression. Respondent number 154 stated, "I am influenced by the Pali Canon's term called eudaimonia, where it differs from temporary, fleeting pressure." Respondent number 168 said that "The voices, the damn voices inside my head." affects her psychological well-being. And lastly, respondent number 78 stated that "Being anxious about the future" affects her psychological well-being. This implies that the psychological factors affect the student's psychological well-being.

Furthermore, the academics of the students also affect the students' psychological well-being with a total of 52(10.04%). The student responded to these academic factors: stress from school due to too many activities, academic pressure, and academic validation. The study of Barbayannis et al. (2022) stated that Academic stress may be the single most dominant stress factor that affects the mental well-being of college students. Respondent number 278 said that "The factor that affects my psychological well-being is too much school work." In addition, other respondents stated that academic validation, stress, and pressure from their parents and peers affect their psychological well-being. This implies that the student's academics affect their psychological well-being.

Finally, socioeconomic factors also affect the students' psychological well-being, with a total response of 10(1.93). In the study written by Rifat and Bithi (2022), Socioeconomic factors affect the performance of students and influence their personal life and mental health too. At an early age, students are being anxious about their socioeconomic status and their position in life. One of the respondents reiterated that "My position in life, family income, and money affects my psychological well-being."

These factors that affect the students' psychological well-being show that even at a young age, they are still feeling anxious about the future and their environment, which greatly contributes to the totality of them as human beings. Therefore, this implies that these factors contribute to positive and negative psychological well-being.

Table 30. *Activities that Saint Mary's University Senior High School Students Engage In to Improve their Mental Health*

Activities	Sample Statements	f	%
Academic	"I study and do my school activities in order to forget my my problems." (51)	13	2.39
Recreational Activities	"I engage in activities like learning instruments, reading fictional and inspirational books, and listening to music." (395)	246	45.30
Sleeping	"Getting a 8 hours well rounded sleep helps me improve the state of my mental health." (404)	47	8.66
Socializing	"I join specific organization which is called <i>happiness project</i> which helps me with upholding my own and others' beliefs as well." (378)	114	20.99
Meditation	"To ease and improve my state of mental health, I take break to relax and escape the burdens of school life. I meditate to manifest a clear mind and I take a 10-minute break to relax everyday."	110	20.26
Others	"Healthy lifestyle such as proper nutrition diet could contribute enormously not only for my mental health but also for my overall well-being." (79)	13	2.39

Table 30 shows students' activities to improve their mental health. According to the table presented, the students' activities were academics, recreational activities, sleeping, socializing, meditation, and others. Recreational activities have the highest frequency, 246(45.30%), and academics and other activities have the lowest frequency, 13(2.39%).

According to the table presented, recreational activities have the highest frequency, with 246(45.30%) of the respondents stating that this helps them improve their mental health. According to an article by Devi (n.d.), Recreational activities enable one to manage stress, whereas they provide a chance to nurture oneself and provide a sense of balance and self-esteem, which can directly reduce anxiety and depression. The recreational activities the students engage in to improve their mental health are watching movies and animes, reading academic and fictional books, playing e-games, traveling, playing sports, exercising, singing, dancing, engaging in vices such as smoking and drinking, biking, and among others. The response of respondent number 24 states, "I find it helpful to find a hobby that can get me away from my own problems, and having my friends with my hobby is a big comfort for me." The study of Y. Takiguchi et al. (2022) states that participating in different leisure activities at a given time increases the level of resilience, which in turn reduces psychological problems. The same results in the study of Congsheng et al. (2022) stated that recreational activities are a key strategy for improving the individual's mental health and well-being benefits. This proves that the students improve their mental health through recreational activities.

In addition, socialization has the second highest frequency, with 114(20.99%) stating that socialization improves their state of mental health. Socialization helps them cope with hard times, lightens their moods, and makes them happier. In addition, socialization reduces the risks of mental health, such as depression (Umberson & Montez, 2011). The different forms of socializing that the students answered were bonding with friends, family, joining organizations at school, and others. The study of Sias and Bartoo (2007) describes friendships as a psychological "vaccine" against both physical and mental illness; it increases the sense of belongingness and purpose. This proves that socializing is a crucial aspect of improving the state of mental health of an individual.

Moreover, meditation is another type of activity to improve the state of mental health. According to the findings of this research, about 110(20.66%) of the respondents state that meditation helps them improve their mental health. Respondent number 195 says, "I meditate to manifest a clear mind, and I make sure to relax." According to the Mayo Clinic (n.d.), meditation can give a sense of calm, peace, and balance that can benefit both emotional well-being and overall health. The different forms of meditation the student engages in include praying, yoga, walking to green spaces, and reflection. According to the American Psychology Association (2019), meditation among healthy people found that meditation-based therapy effectively reduces stress, anxiety, and depression. This implies that meditating alone has a significant impact on improving one's state of mental health.

Furthermore, sleeping also contributes to improving the state of mental health of an individual, whereas according to the results, there are a total of 47 (8.66%) stated that sleeping contributes to improving their state of mental health. According to the statement provided

by respondent number 404, “getting a well-rounded sleep” helps him improve his mental health. According to the Columbia University Department of Psychiatry (2022), sleep helps maintain cognitive skills, such as attention, learning, and memory, such that poor sleep can make it much more challenging to cope with even relatively minor stressors and can even impact our ability to perceive the world accurately. J. Scott et al. (2022) study suggests that improving sleep leads to better mental health. This indicates the importance of sleep among individuals to improve their mental health. And lastly, academics and other activities also help in improving the state of mental health among individuals. With a total frequency of 13(2.39%), it gradually enhances their state of mental health. These activities include doing school activities such as drawing and programming school projects, which gives them the ability to cope with stress. Another activity they engage in to improve their mental health is volunteering for various causes, as respondent 191 stated. According to Hourii (2021), Positive mental health and academic achievement can also powerfully impact one another. This implies that despite the stress and lack of time caused by academics, students always find time and reason to continue their studies and to help other people.

Upon careful analysis of the results of this study, the students have a strong support system for them to grow as better individuals. These activities foster resiliency in their mental capacity. This implies that although the students may encounter problems, they will always find a reason to continue their studies and life.

Conclusion

This study was conducted to determine the relationship between mindset, level of anxiety, and level of psychological well-being of Saint Mary’s University Senior High School students, on which the findings are as follows:

Most students have a growth mindset with some fixed ideas, meaning that they believe that they can achieve proficiency in a specific field with the help of strong belief systems. However, the students also experienced moderate levels of anxiety, which can affect their daily functioning and overall quality of life. Additionally, the students have high psychological well-being, implying that they feel capable and enjoy their lives.

When the students were grouped according to their profile variables, the researchers found a significant difference in the type of mindset based on academic standing. Students with higher academic standing had higher growth mindsets. However, there were no significant differences in mindset based on sex, strand, monthly income of parents, or birth order.

The researchers also found a significant difference on the levels of anxiety based on sex and strands. However, there were no significant differences in anxiety based on socioeconomic status, birth order and academic standing.

Moreover, the researchers found that there was significant difference between the psychological well-being and monthly income of parents which means that SES had a significant influence on the psychological well-being of the students. However, there were no significant differences in the levels of psychological well-being when grouped according to strand, birth order and academic standing.

Moreover, the researchers found a significant relationship between mindset and psychological well-being. Students with higher growth mindsets had higher psychological well-being. However, there was no significant relationship between anxiety and psychological well-being and mindset and anxiety.

Finally, it was found that environment is the major factor that affects the psychological well-being of the students of Saint Mary’s University. Also, students engage in recreational activities to improve their mental health.

Overall, the findings of this study suggest that mindset is an important factor in psychological well-being, even among senior high school students. Additionally, students who are in the STEM strand may be at an increased risk of experiencing anxiety. More research is needed to understand the complex relationship between mindset, anxiety, and psychological well-being, as well as to develop effective interventions to support students' mental health.

After finding out the results of this study, the researchers encourage students to cultivate and nurture a growth mindset and psychological well-being by engaging in recreational activities as well as socializing with good influence people. Given the moderate levels of anxiety experienced by the students, it is important that they should improve their lifestyle by exercising regularly, eating balanced diet and practice mindfulness.

Moreover, the school administration should provide resources and support by implementing interventions and programs that will help students to improve their mindset and psychological well-being, and to lessen their anxiety levels.

Further research is recommended to better assess the relationship between mindset, anxiety, and psychological well-being. The future researchers need to use more concrete and updated questionnaires as well as valid and reliable measurements scale to determine the mindset, anxiety, and psychological well-being of the respondents. Moreover, the researchers should conduct the study in a more diverse population to arrive with better findings and results.

References

Ajmal, M., & Ahmad, S. (2019, August). Exploration of Anxiety Factors among Students of Distance Learning: A Case Study of

Allama Iqbal Open University. Bulletin of Education and Research.

<https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1229454fbclid=IwAR0D7bAjN1GGv4ah59CaWboiu8OwDtyMcmcrxvGaxdNE06X0ya2HcWyBZ3U>

Alampay, L. P., & Garcia, A. S. (n.d.). Education and parenting in the Philippines. APA Dictionary of Psychology. (n.d.). <https://dictionary.apa.org/anxiety>

APA Dictionary of Psychology (n.d.). APA Dictionary of Psychology

Balao, N. Bustillo, R. Canapi, A., Gauani, N., Mateo, S., Pagunuran, C., Taccad, N. (2019, December 11). Study anxiety and scholastic performance of senior high students bustillo et AL20191211 79002 XI9QE2. University Of Saint Louis- Tuguegarao. https://www.academia.edu/41270438/Study_Anxiety_and_Scholastic_Performance_of_Senior_High_Students_Bustillo_et_al20191211_79002_xi9qe2

Botzet, L. J., Rohrer, J. M., & Arslan, R. C. (2021). Analysing effects of birth order on intelligence, educational attainment, big five and risk aversion in an Indonesian sample. *European Journal of Personality*, 35(2), 234- 248.

Bridget L. Forster & Peter R. Reuter (2022). Do college students' living arrangements affect their health behaviors and academic performance?, *Journal of American College Health*.

Buenaobra, J., Espinosa, J., Mohamitano, A. (2021) The Psychological Well- Being and Academic Performance of Filipino Freshmen Tertiary Students Amidst the New Normal of Education.

Chand, S. P. (2023, April 24). Anxiety. StatPearls - NCBI Bookshelf. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK470361/>

Chen, M., & Xiao, X. (2022) The effect of social media on the development Children: Results From A-CHILD Study. *Frontiers*.

Definition of MINDSET. (2023, April 22).

Department of Health (DOH). (2020). "Your mind matters: DOH calls for a unified response to mental health." <https://doh.gov.ph/press-release/Your-mind-matters-DOH-calls-for-unified-response-to-mental-health>.

Destin, M., Hanselman, P., Buontempo, J., Tipton, E., & Yeager, D. S. (2019). Do Student Mindsets Differ by Socioeconomic Status and Explain Disparities in Academic Achievement in the United States? *AERA Open*, 5(3).

Dweck, C.S. (2006) *Mindset: The new psychology of success*. New York House Inc.

Ericson A. (2022). The Role of Deliberate Practice in the Acquisition of Expert Performance. [https://graphics8.nytimes.com/images/blogs/freakonomics/pdf/DeliberatePractice\(PsychologicalReview\).pdf](https://graphics8.nytimes.com/images/blogs/freakonomics/pdf/DeliberatePractice(PsychologicalReview).pdf)

Ferguson, H., Bovaird, S., & Mueller, M. (2007). The impact of poverty on educational outcomes for children. *Paediatrics & child health*, 12(8), 701– 706. <https://doi.org/10.1093/pch/12.8.701>

Fukuya, Y., Fujiwara, T., Isumi, A., Doi, S., & Ochi, M. (2021). Association of Birth Order With Mental Health Problems, Self-Esteem, Resilience, and Happiness Among Children: Results From A-CHILD Study. *Frontiers in psychiatry*, 12, 638088.

Furnham, A., & Treglown, L. (2021). Sex differences in personality scores on six scales: Many significant, but mostly small, differences. *Current Psychology: A Journal for Diverse Perspectives on Diverse Psychological Issues*. Advance online publication.

Griffin, J. JR. (1990). Anxiety. In: Walker HK, Hall WD, Hurst JW, editors. *Clinical Methods: The History, Physical, and Laboratory Examinations*. 3rd edition. Boston: Butterworths; Chapter 202. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK315/>

Gubits, D., Shinn, M., Wood, M., Brown, S. R., Dastrup, S. R., & Bell, S. H. (2019) What Interventions Work Best for Families Who Experience Homelessness? Impact Estimates From the Family Options Study.

Hashmat, S., Hashmat, M., Amanullah, F., & Aziz, S. (2008). Factors causing exam anxiety in medical students. *JPMA. The Journal of the Pakistan Medical Association*, 58(4), 167–170.

Hao, Y., & Farah, M. J. (2020). The affective neuroscience of socioeconomic status: implications for mental health. *BJPsych bulletin*, 44(5), 202–207. <https://doi.org/10.1192/bjb.2020.69>

Ibcces. (2020, April 17). Impact of anxiety and depression on student academic progress. *IBCCES*. <https://ibcces.org/blog/2019/05/01/impact-anxiety-depression-student-progress/>

Jiang, Y., Liu, H., Yao, Y., Li, Q., & Li, Y. (2023). The Positive Effects of Growth Mindset on Students' Intention toward Self-Regulated Learning during the COVID-19 Pandemic: A PLS-SEM Approach. *Sustainability*, 15(3), 2180. MDPI AG.

Kılınçel, Ş., Kılınçel, O., Muratdağı, G., Aydın, A., & Usta, M. B. (2021). Factors affecting the anxiety levels of adolescents in home-

- quarantine during COVID-19 pandemic in Turkey. *Asia-Pacific psychiatry : official journal of the Pacific Rim College of Psychiatrists*, 13(2), e12406. <https://doi.org/10.1111/appy.12406>
- King, M. F., Renó, V. F., & Novo, E. M. L. M. (2014). The Concept, Dimensions and Methods of Assessment of Human Well-Being within a Socioecological Context: A Literature Review. *Social Indicators Research*, 116(3), 681–698.
- Kubzansky, L. D., Huffman, J. C., Boehm, J. K., Hernandez, R., Kim, E. S., Koga, H. K., Feig, E. H., Lloyd-Jones, D. M., Seligman, M. E. P., & Labarthe, D.R. (2018). Positive Psychological Well-Being and Cardiovascular Disease: JACC Health Promotion Series. *Journal of the American College of Cardiology*, 72(12), 1382–1396.
- Laftman, S. B., Almquist, Y. B., & Östberg, V. (2013). ERIC - EJ1035184 - Students' Accounts of School-Performance Stress: A Qualitative Analysis of a High-Achieving Setting in Stockholm, Sweden, *Journal of Youth Studies*, 2013. ERIC -EJ1035184 - Students' Accounts of School- Performance Stress: A Qualitative Analysis of a High-Achieving Setting in Stockholm, Sweden. *Journal of Youth Studies*.
- Lally, J., Tully, J., & Samaniego, R. (2019). Mental health services in the Philippines. *BJPsych international*, 16(3), 62–64.
- Lcsw, A. M. (2022, February 11). How to Improve your Psychological Well-Being. *Verywell Mind*. <https://www.verywellmind.com/improve-psychological-well-being-4177330#:~:text=Studies%20have%20discovered%20that%20people,a%20associated%20with%20fewer%20social%20problems.>
- Li H, Hafeez H and Zaheer MA (2021) COVID-19 and Pretentious Psychological Well- Being of Students: A Threat to Educational Sustainability. *Front. Psychol.*11:628003.
- Limeri, L. B., Carter, N. T., Choe, J., Harper, H. G., Martin, H. R., Benton, A., & Dolan, E. L. (2020). Growing a growth mindset: characterizing how and why undergraduate students' mindsets change. *International Journal of STEM Education* 7, 35.
- Mabandos, S. M. Y., & Moneva, J. C. (2020). Students' Mindset and Level of Anxiety for General Mathematics among Grade 11 Students: A Case of Jagobiao National High School, Philippines. *IRA International Journal of Education and Multidisciplinary Studies*, 16(1), 28. <https://doi.org/10.21013/jems.v16.n1.p6>
- Madhu G. R., Praveenkumar L., and Mahaveer M. N. (2021) A Study on the Level of Psychological Well-Being Between Yoga and Mallakhamba Trainees: A Comparative. *International Journal For Innovative Research In Multidisciplinary Field*.
- Margolis, S., & Lyubomirsky, S. (2020). Experimental manipulation of extraverted and introverted behavior and its effects on well-being. *Journal of Experimental Psychology: General*.
- Matud, M.P., López-Curbelo, M., Fortes, D. (2019). Gender and Psychological WellBeing. *Int J Environ Res Public Health*.
- McLean, C. P., Asnaani, A., Litz, B. T., & Hofmann, S. G. (2011). Gender differences in anxiety disorders: prevalence, course of illness, comorbidity and burden of illness. *Journal of psychiatric research*, 45(8), 1027–1035. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpsychires.2011.03.006>
- Mental Health CDC. (2023). Centers for Disease Control and Prevention. <https://www.cdc.gov/mentalhealth/index.htm/>
- Morales-Rodríguez, F. M., Espigares-López, I., Brown, T., & Pérez-Mármol, J.M. (2020). The Relationship between Psychological Well-Being and Psychosocial Factors in University Students. *International journal of environmental research and public health*, 17(13), 4778. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17134778>
- Morin, A., (2022). How to Improve Your Psychological Well-Being. *Very Well Mind*. <https://www.verywellmind.com/improve-psychological-well-being-4177330>
- Multisari, Widya, Rachmawati, Indriyana, Hidayatur Rahman, Diniy, Bagus Priambodo, Aji, & Da Costa (2022). Psychological well-being of students in completing their final projects. *Pegem Journal of Education and Instruction*, 13(1), 259–266. <https://doi.org/10.47750/pegegog.13.01.28>
- Mustafa, M. B., Rani, N. H. M., Bistaman, M. N., Salim, S. S. S., Ahmad, A., Zakaria, N. H., & Safian, N. A. A. (2020). The Relationship between Psychological Well- Being and University Students Academic Achievement. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 10(7), 518– 525.
- Naceanceno, Kendall D.; Capps, Sara K.; Whittenburg, Rachel; and Ortiz, Alexis (2021) “A Comparison of Anxiety Levels Among College Students,” *Journal of Graduate Education Research: Vol. 2 , Article 8*. <https://scholarworks.harding.edu/jger/vol2/iss1/8>
- Navarro-Carrillo G, Alonso-Ferres M, Moya M and Valor-Segura I (2020) Socioeconomic Status and Psychological Well-Being: Revisiting the Role of Subjective Socioeconomic Status. *Front. Psychol.* 11:1303.
- Nomaguchi, K. M., Milkie, M. A., & Bianchi, S. B (2005). Time strains and psychological well- being: Do dual-earner mothers and fathers differ? *Journal of Family Issues*.

- Panchal, N., Saunders, S., Rudowitz, R. & Cox, C. (2023). The Implications of COVID- 19 for Mental Health and Substance Use. Kaiser Family Foundation.
- Partners, C. (2018). The Impact of Mindset on Your Achievement - LeadershipCoaching | Change Partners. Leadership Coaching | Change Partners - Unlocking Leadership Potential.
- Perez, J. (2012). Gender Difference in Psychological Well-being among Filipino College Student Samples. International Journal of Humanities and Social Science.
- Remes, O., Mendes, J. F., & Templeton, P. (2021). Biological, Psychological, and Social Determinants of Depression: A Review of Recent Literature. *Brain sciences*, 11(12), 1633. <https://doi.org/10.3390/brainsci11121633>
- Robert. (2015) Settling the Debate on Birth Order and Personality.
- Rohrer, D., & Egloff, B. (2018). Does birth order affect personality? Meta-analysis of studies of Big Five traits, intelligence, and risk aversion.
- Romero, C. (2015). What We Know About Growth Mindset from Scientific Research. <https://studentexperiencenetwork.org/wp-content/uploads/2015/09/What-We-Know-About-Growth-Mindset.pdf> *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 116(1), 131-1
- Russell, D., & Breaux, E. (2019, May 11). Living Arrangements in Later Life. *Encyclopedia of Gerontology and Population Aging*. DOI:10.1007/978-3- 319- 69892-2
- Ryff, C. D. (1989). Happiness is everything, or is it? Explorations on the meaning of psychological well-being. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 57(6), 1069-1081.
- Şahin, S., & Tuna, R. (2022). The effect of anxiety on thriving levels of university students during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Collegian*; Elsevier BV. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.colegn.2021.10.004>
- Salleh, Nurul & Mustaffa, Che Su. (2016). Examining the Differences of Gender on Psychological Well-being. *International Review of Management and Marketing*. 6. 82-87.
- Schenck, L. (2011). Myers-Briggs: 8 Introverted. *Mindfulness Muse*.
- Schivinski, B., Brzozowska-Woś, M., Stansbury, E., Satel, J., Montag, C., and Pontes, H. (2020) Exploring the Role of Social Media Use Motives, Psychological Well Being, Self- Esteem, and Affect in Problematic Social Media Use. *Front. Psychol.*11:617140.
- Seifert, T. (2005). The Ryff Scales of Psychological Well-Being. Center of Inquiry at Wabash College.
- Sharma, G., Srimathi N., (2014). Do Psychological Well-Being characteristics vary with Birth Order? *IOSR Journal Of Humanities And Social Science*.
- Salleh, N.B. & Mustafa, C.B. “Examining the Differences of Gender on Psychological Well-being.” *Int Rev Manag Market* 6.8 (2016): 82-87.
- Smiley, P. A., Buttitta, K. V., Chung, S. Y., Dubon, V. X., & Chang, L. K. (2016) Mediation Models of Implicit Theories and Achievement Goals Predict Planning and Withdrawal After Failure - Motivation and Emotion.
- Stannard, S., Berrington, A., & Alwan, N. A. (2019). Associations between birth order with mental wellbeing and psychological distress in midlife: Findings from the 1970 British Cohort Study (BCS70). *PLOS ONE*, 14(9), e0222184. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0222184>
- Stufano, A., Lucchese, G., Stahl, B., Grattagliano, I., Dassisti, L., Lovreglio, P., Flöel, A., & Iavicoli, I. (2022). Impact of COVID-19 emergency on the psychological well- being of susceptible individuals. *Scientific reports*, 12(1), 11152.
- Symister P., & Friend R (2003). The influence of social support and problematic support on optimism and depression in chronic illness: A prospective study evaluating self-esteem as a mediator. *Health Psychology*.
- Tang, Y-Y., Tang, R., and Gross, JJ. (2019) Promoting Psychological Well- Being Through an Evidence-Based Mindfulness Training Program.
- Tao, W., Zhao, D., Yue, H., Horton, I., Tian, X., Xu, Z., & Sun, H. J. (2022). The Influence of Growth Mindset on the Mental Health and Life Events of College Students. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13, 821206.
- Thurstans, S., Opondo, C., Seal, A., Wells, J., Khara, T., Dolan, C., ... & Kerac, M. (2020). Boys are more likely to be undernourished than girls: a systematic review and meta-analysis of sex differences in undernutrition. *BMJ global health*, 5(12), e004030.
- Tus, J., Paras, N., Espiritu, N., Perante, L., Dalmacio, J., Dianito, A., Bartolome, R., University, S. (2021) Your powerful, changeable mindset. *Stanford Report*.

Twigg, L., Duncan, C., & Weich, S. (2020). Is social media use associated with children's well-being? Results from the UK Household Longitudinal Study. *Journal of adolescence*, 80, 73–83.

Valtolina, Giovanni & Colombo, Chiara. (2012). Psychological Well-Being, Family Relations, and Developmental Issues of Children Left Behind. *Psychological reports*.

Villani, L., Pastorino, R., Molinari, E. et al. Impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on psychological well-being of students in an Italian university: a web-based cross-sectional survey. *Global Health* 17, 39 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12992-021-00680-w> World Health Organization (2022). *Mental Health*.

Waghmare, R.D. “A Study of Psychological Well Being among Male and Female College Students.” *Int J Indian Psychol* 3.3 (2016): 27-30.

World Health Organization (2021). Mental health of adolescents. <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/adolescent-mental-health>

World Health Organization: WHO. (2022, June). Mental disorders. https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/mental-disorders/gclid=Cj0KCQiAnrOtBhDIARIsAFsSe50ceQfi5GqzXifDimnT7zRAsD0FTvxRJNCzP82qZRVk9hUVO8FnMW8aAuDqEALw_wcB

Zeng, G., Hou, H., & Peng, K. (2016). Effect of growth mindset on school engagement and psychological well-being of Chinese primary and middle school students: The mediating role of resilience. *Frontiers in psychology*,

Zhang, Y., & Ma, Z. F. (2020). Impact of the COVID-19 Pandemic on Mental Health and Quality of Life among Local Residents in Liaoning Province, China: A Cross- Sectional Study. *International journal of environmental research and public health*, 17(7), 2381.

Zhou, S., Gao, L., Liu, F., Tian, W., Jin, Y., & Zheng, Z. (2021) Socioeconomic Status and Depressive Symptoms in Older People With the Mediation Role of Social Support: A Population-based Longitudinal Study. *PubMed Central (PMC)*

Zhuang-Shuang L. and Hasson F. (2020) Resilience, stress, and psychological well-being in nursing students: A systematic review. *Nurse education today*

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